
Impacts of Phosphates on Water Quality and Aquatic Life

Hamza Badamasi*, Muhammad N. Yaro, Ali Ibrahim, Iliyasu A. Bashir

Department of Chemistry, Federal University Dutse, Dutse-Nigeria

*Corresponding author's e-mail: hamza.badamasi@fud.edu.ng

Abstract Development of industrialization and increasing agricultural activities have resulted in excessive Phosphates concentrations in water bodies. Phosphorus is the second most important plant nutrient after nitrogen and is essential for optimal growth of plants and animals, yet at certain concentration levels, it is usually considered to be a pollutant. The excessive Phosphorus fertilization of water bodies is a long-standing, well-recognized water quality problem throughout the world. Phosphorus is recognized as one of the major nutrients contributing to the increased eutrophication of lakes and other natural waters. This has led to many water quality problems including increased purification costs, interference with the recreational and conservation value of impoundments, loss of livestock and the possible sub-lethal effects of algae toxins on humans using eutrophic water supplies for drinking. It is therefore necessary to determine the levels of phosphates and its species in water bodies to provide essential data for assessing the health of ecosystems; investigating biogeochemical processes and monitoring compliance with legislation. This paper therefore examined the impacts of phosphates on water quality and its effects on aquatic organism.

Keywords Phosphates, Water Quality, Aquatic Life

Introduction

Phosphates

Phosphates are oxide of phosphorus, and it's one of the common pollutants in water. Phosphorus is the eleventh most abundant element on the surface of the earth and is most commonly found as phosphate (Cairl *et al.*, 2003). Phosphorus is a very reactive non-metal, it is therefore never found in uncombined state. It is found in the earth crust, largely as ores, such as flourapatite [$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{F}_2$] and hydroxyapatite [$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{H}_2\text{O}$] (Harris, 2002). Phosphorus is the second most abundant element in our bodies, found mostly in our bones and teeth [1].

Form of Phosphates

There are four classifications of phosphates often referred to in environmental literature [2];

- i. Orthophosphates are the inorganic forms of phosphate, such as PO_4^{3-} , HPO_4^{2-} and H_2PO_4^+ . These are the forms of phosphates used heavily in fertilizers and are often introduced to surface waters through runoff.
- ii. Organically bound phosphates are found in human and animal wastes or in decaying organic matter.
- iii. Condensed phosphates (also called polyphosphates), such as $\text{P}_3\text{O}_{10}^{5-}$, are sometimes added to water supplies and industrial processes to prevent the formation of scaling and to inhibit corrosion. This is the form of phosphate that was commonly found in detergents in the past.

- iv. Total phosphates are the sum of all three of the forms described above. This is the most commonly reported form of phosphate concentration.

Sources of Phosphates

The two main sources of phosphate in water are natural and through anthropogenic activities. Natural source includes leaching of phosphate from rock deposits and anthropogenic activities include use of detergent, decomposition of organic waste, agricultural runoff and industrial effluents [3]. Phosphates are added to surface waters by a variety of means. Humans add phosphates to water through industrial and agricultural wastes. Fertilizers contain high levels of phosphates and will enter the water by means of runoff and soil erosion. In areas where land and vegetation have been disturbed, soil erosion will increase. This will lead to even more phosphates being washed out of the soil and into the water. Phosphates can also come from the excrement of animals living in or near the water. The use of fertilizers (phosphates) by farmers increases on daily basis due to the increasing demands for agricultural produce. The positive outcomes of the application of these fertilizers, such as, increasing in food produce, nutrients of the soil have always been focus, thereby neglecting the negative impacts [4].

In Nigeria, High phosphate values may be due to wastes emanating from homes, abattoir, sawmills, food processing industries, chemical/pharmaceutical industries, soap/detergents industries and car washing activities [5].

Uses of Phosphates

Phosphorus is the second most important plant nutrient after nitrogen [6]. Phosphorus is an essential component of adenosine triphosphate (ATP), which is involved in most biochemical processes in plants and enables them to extract nutrients from the soil. Phosphorus also plays a critical role in cell development and DNA formation. Insufficient soil Phosphorus can result in delayed crop maturity, reduced flower development, low seed quality, and decreased crop yield [7]. In recent years, large quantities of phosphate have been used in beverages [8], detergents [9], and fertilizers and also in sugar industries [10]. Phosphate that is put into our drinking water to prevent lead poisoning can potentially cause environmental damage as a result of leakage.

Uses of Phosphates in Detergents

About 5% of the total phosphate mined worldwide is used in detergents. The chemical form in which phosphate is used in detergents is predominantly pentasodium triphosphate (PSTP). The most significant feature for the use of PSTP in detergents is its ability to form soluble and strong complexes with calcium and magnesium ions. Other important features of PSTP are its ability disperse dirt in washing solution, its weak alkalinity and its toxicological acceptability [11].

Uses of Phosphates in Drinking Water

Phosphorus is routinely added to drinking water supplies in a form known as phosphate. It is added to effectively prevent any lead entering the water supply, which can come from the corrosion of old piping. Lead is a toxic metal and adding phosphate has proven to be very successful in reducing human exposure to it [12].

Phosphates Control Measures

Control of phosphorus sources to the environment will continue to be important because almost all elevated levels of phosphorus in water bodies are due to anthropogenic sources. The following are some measures to be taken to control the effects of excessive phosphates in water bodies [13]:

- i. The government should introduce Phosphate detergent bans
- ii. Effluent phosphorus limits
- iii. Nonpoint-Source controls on phosphorus
- iv. Use best management practices to reduce phosphate levels such practices include crop rotation, erosion and runoff prevention to avoid phosphorus losses and protect soil-water quality.
- v. the use of phosphate containing agricultural materials such as fertilizers, herbicides,

- vi. Fungicides should be reduce and the farmers should be enlighten on the negative impact of over dependence of phosphate materials can cause.
- vii. Phosphate removal can be achieved by Enhanced Biological Phosphate Removal' ('EBPR') which utilizes the ability of some microorganisms to accumulate phosphate (as polyphosphate) in excess of their normal metabolic requirements.
- viii. Prevent livestock from entering water sources

Phosphorus Cycle

The phosphorus cycle is the biogeochemical cycle that describes the movement of phosphorus through the lithosphere, hydrosphere, and biosphere. Unlike many other biogeochemical cycles, the atmosphere does not play a significant role in the movements of phosphorus, because phosphorus and phosphorus-based compounds are usually solids at the typical ranges of temperature and pressure found on Earth [14]. Phosphorus moves slowly from deposits on land and in sediments, to living organisms, and then much more slowly back into the soil and water sediment as shown in figure 1. The general phosphorus transformation processes are: weathering and precipitation, mineralization and immobilization, and adsorption and desorption.

Figure 1: Phosphorus Cycle (adapted from Pierzynski *et al.*, [14]). SOM stands for soil organic matter

Water

Water is one of the most important and abundant compounds of the ecosystem. All living organisms on the earth need water for their survival and growth [15]. Water is one of the major constituents of the earth. Based on the geographical analysis, the earth crust is covered with 70 % of water (sea, river, lakes). Water is a vital source of

human existence since body of man is made up of 70% water and gets thirsty when 1% loss of the fluid even risks death when up to 10% loss of the fluid. Water must not only be adequate in quantity but also in quality. Man needs water for drinking, cooking, bathing, sewage disposal, irrigation for agriculture, industrial uses and for recreational purposes, transportation, life stock production, hydroelectric power generation, building construction, fishing and agriculture. Its deficiency causes most of the ill- health which affects humanity especially in developing countries where there are not much availability and accessibility in quantity and quality of water for human consumption and other activities which needs water for its efficiency. Death due to water related diseases sums up to more than 3 million people per year [16]. Water is generally classified into surface water and ground water. The surface water is found in river, lake, oceans, streams or superficial cavities such as dug well. Surface water is exposed to many different contaminants, such as animal wastes, industrial wastes etc. Ground water on the other hand is water which is trapped beneath the ground. Rain that soaks into the ground, rivers that disappear beneath the earth. Ground water may contain any or all the contaminants found in surface water as well as the dissolved minerals it picks up during the long stay underground.

Water Quality

Water quality describes the condition of water, including chemical, physical and biological characteristics, usually with respect to its suitability for a particular purpose such as drinking or swimming [17]. Water quality is measured by several factors, such as the concentrations of dissolved oxygen, bacteria levels, the amount of salts or the amount of suspended materials. Other parameters include nitrates, phosphates, chlorides etc.

Phosphates and Water Quality

Phosphorus is an important nutrient for plant growth. In aquatic systems, a lack of phosphorus often limits aquatic plant growth. Excess phosphorus is usually considered to be a pollutant. Phosphorus is recognized as one of the major nutrients contributing to the increased eutrophication of lakes and other natural waters. This has led to many water quality problems including increased purification costs, interference with the recreational and conservation value of impoundments, loss of livestock and the possible sub-lethal effects of alga toxins on humans using eutrophic water supplies for drinking. Agricultural practices could have negative impacts on surface water and in terms of the degradation in water quality especially in rural based settings. Since farming is the major occupation in the rural area, chemical fertilizers such as Nitrogen Phosphorus Potassium (NPK), urea and manure are widely applied on agricultural farm lands to improve crop yield thereby compromising the quality of the water sources [18].

Water Quality Problems Caused by Excessive Phosphate Fertilization

High phosphate levels will result in the eutrophication of the river. Growth of algae in the river will be supported by the phosphate. As the algae die, they are decomposed in the water by microorganisms which consume the dissolved oxygen making the river unable to support aquatic life. This anaerobic conditions might have been responsible for having the water septic, changing the colour, reducing stable minerals and producing oxides with offensive odour [19]. The equations below show the sequence reactions that take place during eutrophication of water:

- i. $\text{CO}_2 + \text{N} + \text{P} \rightarrow \text{algae} + \text{O}_2$
- ii. $\text{Algae} + \text{O}_2 + \text{decay\& death} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{NH}_3$
- iii. $\text{NH}_3 + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{NO}_3^-$
- iv. $\text{POM} + \text{Bacteria} + \text{O}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO}_2$ [19].

Domestic Water Supplies

Planktonic algae can have a severe impact on domestic water supply water quality through shortened filter runs, the release of organic compounds that cause tastes and odors, and, in some instances, the production of trihalomethane (THM) precursors. The THMs are chloroform and chloroform-like compounds which are formed during the disinfection of water supplies. They are regulated as human carcinogens. Water utilities experience increased cost of treatment if the raw water supply has excessive algae and some other aquatic plants [19].

Violations of Water Quality Standard

The excessive fertilization of water bodies can lead to marked night to day changes in pH and dissolved oxygen concentrations. The photosynthesis/ respiratory changes are the result of algal removal of CO₂ from the water, which, by late afternoon, can cause the pH of the water to increase above the water quality standard. Accompanying algal growth, which occurs in light, there is production of oxygen. However, in the dark, the algae and other organisms in the water are only respiring, which results in the release of CO₂, lowering the pH, with a concomitant consumption of oxygen. The dissolved oxygen in a water body just before sunrise can be sufficiently low to violate water quality standards for protection of fish and other aquatic life [20].

Impact on Fisheries

Fish kills associated with toxic algae are not new; they have been occurring in various water bodies around the world for many years. As the algae die, they are decomposed in the water by microorganisms which consume the dissolved oxygen making the fish unable to survive [21-22].

Impaired Recreation

Excessive growths of algae, both planktonic and attached, can affect the use of water bodies for swimming, boating and fishing, through interference with water contact. They can also lead to severe odor problems due to decaying algae and algal scums [21].

Relationship between Phosphates on Some Water Quality Parameters

Phosphates in the soil depend on some parameters such as pH, moisture content, and temperature. Temperature and pH conditions may aid oxidation of organophosphorous compounds to inorganic phosphates [23]. Excess phosphates in water always lead to increased biological oxygen demand (BOD) and decreased in dissolved oxygen (DO) [21]. There is positive correlation between phosphates, nitrates and chlorides [18].

Phosphate Recommended Limits

Phosphates are essential for plants and animal proper growth and development. Excess phosphate is however considered to be pollutant. There is therefore a need to regulate the amount of phosphate entering the water bodies. To control eutrophication, the USEPA has established a recommended limit of 0.05 mg/L for total phosphates in streams that enter lakes and 0.1 mg/L for total phosphorus in flowing waters [24]. According to World health organization [16], the phosphate maximum allowable limit is 5 mg/L. In Nigeria, the established water quality Criteria by FEPA, Federal Environmental Protection Agency [25] after the illegal dumping of toxins in Koko Port in the then Bendel State: Nitrate 20 mg/L for surface water, Phosphates 5 mg/L for surface water and 10 mg/L for land use.

Eutrophication

Eutrophication is the leading cause of impairment in freshwater and coastal marine ecosystem in the world. Eutrophication is a natural process whereby lakes, rivers, estuaries and slow-moving streams receive excess nutrients as a consequence of weatherly of rocks and soil from the surrounding water shed [2]. The increased nutrient (phosphorus) leads to an increased growth of aquatic plants and organic production of the water body. Although phosphorus is a nutrient essential to the growth of plants, too much of a good thing can be harmful to the environment. Enriched phosphorus levels can accelerate the growth of algae and other plants that impair the suitability of the water for municipal, recreational, and fishery use [26].

Phosphorus and Eutrophication

Phosphorus generally is the limiting nutrient in eutrophication [27] because the ratio of phosphorus in plant content to its availability in water is larger than for any other nutrient [28]. Therefore, under typical freshwater conditions where physical factors are conducive to the growth of algae, additions of phosphorus to the system are more likely to lead to accelerated growth than are additions of other nutrients. This view was held strongly enough in 1974 that an International Congress of Limnologists ratified a resolution emphasizing the critical role of phosphorus in eutrophication [28]. However, more recent studies indicate that increased nitrogen and phosphorus together stimulate growth the most [29]. Murdoch *et al* [30] argues that high level of phosphate and nitrate can lead to eutrophication, which increases algae growth and ultimately reduces dissolved oxygen levels in the water. Lundberg, [31] stated that eutrophication will cause hypoxia and anoxia in aquatic life as a result of sedimentation associated with primary production. Phosphate increase may be due to increase in concentration of phytoplankton and zooplankton excreta [32]. According to Sharma [33] and Sharma *et al.* [34], phosphorus could be considered as an important index for the evolution and comparison of trophic level of water bodies spatially for the short duration limnological surveys. Murphy and Riley [35] standardized the methods for quantification of phosphorus showed a direct relation with plankton and it was observed that the plankton flourish well during the period of high concentration of phosphate. The reduction in phosphate immediately after the phytoplankton peak showed its utilization by the algal community.

Eutrophication in Nigeria

Eutrophication is a threat to the water quality of rivers, lakes and reservoirs, hence their classification into oligotrophic, mesotrophic and eutrophic based on level of eutrophication [36]. Recently in Nigeria eutrophication rates in water bodies have increased dramatically as a result of alterations in nutrient cycles related to land use. The increasing demand for food and food insecurity which has the increased use of fertilizers on farmland has been pointed out as contributing over 80% of eutrophication of water bodies' worldwide. Adeyemo *et al* [37] observes that land use around riverine areas in Nigeria is predominantly for farmland and this could be explanation for the high level of phosphate from run-off during rainy season in Ibadan River. Nweze and Onyishi [38] indicated that indiscriminate use of fertilizers around Nike Lake in Enugu, Nigeria is the major source of pollution causing Cyanophycean blooms and ecological disaster. Since the population boom in Nigeria in the 80's the use of N.P.K fertilizer has increased and led to the treat observed in water bodies located close to these farmland. When washed as a result of erosion, flooding increased the nutrient load of these water bodies. Other anthropogenic activities that can cause eutrophication in water bodies include increased silt, deforestation, lumbering activities and other land use perturbation.

Effects of Phosphate Leaching and Its Implications on Water Quality

Leaching is a process that describes the eluviation of solutes through the soil profile in percolating water [39]. Phosphorus application in excess of plant requirements may result in increased leaching. Leaching of Phosphorus into ground water bodies followed by the discharge of Phosphorus-enriched ground water into surface water bodies can lead to eutrophication [14]. It has been well documented that the main cause of eutrophication of surface freshwater bodies (lakes, reservoir, rivers, streams, and head waters of estuarine systems) is excessive Phosphorus concentrations [40]. Surface water eutrophication causes an increase in primary production (algae, phytoplankton, macrophytes), oxygen depletion, fish kills and reduction of aquatic biodiversity, it also causes a reduction in water clarity, substitution of phytoplankton with blue green algae which produce toxins that threatens human and animal health, it increases water treatment costs (due to taste and odor problems caused by algae and algae removal), it impairs waters for recreational activities and reduces the value of shoreline properties [40-41]. Heavy rainfall, especially soon after application of fertilizer has been reported to increase the amount of Phosphorus leaching [42]. Several authors have reported an increase in leaching from turf grasses in response to excessive irrigation rates [43-45].

Methods of Determining Phosphates in Water

The determination of phosphorus species in environmental matrices provides essential data for assessing the health of ecosystems and monitoring compliance with legislation. There are some analytical methods used for the determination of different phosphate concentrations in water; these are titrimetry [46] and complex-gravimetry [47]. Also, there are some methods that are applicable to determination of phosphates at ppm levels; colorimetry [48], high-performance liquid chromatography [49], ion chromatography [50] and spectroscopy [51]. Spectroscopic method of determination is one of the common methods nowadays for phosphate determination. The most common methods are molybdovanadate and ammonium molybdate. The most common and established method for the determination of phosphate is spectrophotometric molybdenum blue method. The process involves the formation of molybdophosphoric acid from ortho phosphate and an excess of molybdate in acidic solution followed by reduction to give molybdenum blue. In ammonium molybdate method, there are some commonly used reductants; tin (II) chloride [52], ascorbic acid [53] and hydrazine sulphate [54]. The absorbance of phosphates in the samples was measured spectrophotometrically at a certain wavelength (λ_{max}) that gives maximum absorbance. The intensity of the blue colour is proportional to the amount of phosphate present in the sample solution. The equation for the reactions are shown below;

Summary

Indispensable for life, water is one of the most important and abundant compounds of the ecosystem. Water quality is direct indicator for the general health and wellbeing of the populace. Water quality can be impaired by increased levels of Phosphates loads from municipal, agricultural and industrial wastes. Phosphates present in the environment are not toxic to people or animals unless they are present in very high concentration. They are one of the key elements necessary for the growth and development of plants and animals. Growth of algae and other aquatic microphytes in water will be supported by the phosphate resulting in algal blooms. When algal blooms exhaust the supply of phosphorus, they die and start to decompose. During decomposition, dissolved oxygen is removed from the water by micro-organisms that break down the organic material. The lack of dissolved oxygen makes it difficult for aquatic organisms to survive. It is well documented that phosphate is one of the key parameter that causes eutrophication of water bodies. Eutrophication causes reduced aesthetic and recreational value of lakes, river and stream as well as the seasonal depletion of the water dissolved oxygen content, which may result in death of fish as well as other ecosystem disruptions. It is therefore paramount importance to determine and monitor the levels of phosphates in the water bodies to provide essential and reliable data for assessing the health of ecosystems, investigating biogeochemical processes and monitoring compliance with the environmental regulatory.

Conclusion

Phosphorus is an important nutrient for optimal growth of both plants and animals. In aquatic systems, lack of phosphorus often limits aquatic life growth. However, excessive phosphorus is usually considered to be a pollutant. Phosphates is recognized as one of the major nutrients contributing to the increased eutrophication of lakes and other natural waters. This has led to many water quality problems including increased purification costs, interference with the recreational and conservation value of impoundments, loss of livestock and the possible sub-lethal effects of alga toxins on humans using eutrophic water supplies for drinking. It is therefore necessary to determine the levels of phosphorus species in the environmental matrices to provide essential data for assessing the health of ecosystems, investigating biogeochemical processes and monitoring compliance with legislation.

Recommendations

The following recommendations should be considered for management of phosphates load in our bodies:

- i. For the effective management of phosphates load of water bodies, both point and non-point sources of pollution must be taken into recognition and controlled.
- ii. Strict compliance with the guidelines of regulatory bodies such W.H.O, NESREA, and NAFDAC should be imposed on the effluent phosphates limits
- iii. There is need for the government to monitor the contributing factors of increased phosphates in water systems and create awareness on the adverse health effects the consumption of these waters can cause.
- iv. The Federal Government and the Ministry of Environment must set huge amount from the ecological funds for proper evaluating by hydrobiologist and toxicologist in the nation.
- v. The Federal Government should impose Phosphate Detergent Bans especially in detergents and other industrial products
- vi. Use best management practices to reduce phosphate levels such practices include crop rotation, erosion and runoff prevention to avoid phosphorus losses and protect soil-water quality

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